

IMPROVING EUROPEAN DEMOCRACY AND LEGITIMACY FOR CRISIS AND POST-CRISIS TIMES

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Culminating more than a decade of crisis in Europe, the Covid-19 pandemic has opened an important window of opportunity for institutional and policy change, not only at the “reactive” level of emergency responses, but also to tackle more broadly the many socio-political challenges caused or exacerbated by Covid-19. Building on this premise, the Horizon Europe project REGROUP (*Rebuilding governance and resilience out of the pandemic*) aims to: 1) provide the European Union with a body of actionable advice on how to rebuild post-pandemic governance and public policies in an effective and democratic way; anchored to 2) a map of the socio-political dynamics and consequences of Covid-19; and 3) an empirically-informed normative evaluation of the pandemic.

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Executive summary

Building on previous tasks, this paper takes stock of the state of Europe's multi-level democracy and legitimacy in crisis times and makes recommendations on how to safeguard both principles. We recommend a system of democratic auditing in good times and bad.

Our **first recommendation** is that there should be regular 5-year democratic audits of the EU and of Member State Democracies (MSDs) before European elections, so that the results of the audits are available for citizens to assess during the EP election campaign. This assures that the democratic audit is directly politically relevant.

Our **second recommendation** is that there should also be special democratic audits of the handling of emergencies. That will require a double adaptation of democratic auditing i) to the EU and ii) to emergency politics. To adapt democratic auditing to the case of the EU and its member state democracies (MSDs) we recommend developing indicators of how well the EU and MSDs comply with input, output, and throughput standards of democratic legitimacy. See also the indicators we developed in the initial REGROUP application and our earlier paper (Fossum and Lord 2023). To adapt democratic auditing of the EU and its MSD's to the special problem of emergency politics, we recommend developing additional indicators. These could include but go beyond indicators based on the Council of Europe standards for emergency politics. For Council of Europe standards, see also our earlier paper (Fossum and Lord 2023).

Our **third recommendation** is that for the democratic audits of EU and MSD responses to emergencies we recommend process traces of key decisions. The process traces should shed added light on how well decisions taken by the EU and MSDs at critical junctures in their handling of emergencies meet the standards set out in our indicators of democratic standards under conditions of emergency.¹

Our **fourth recommendation** is to collect and systematize as much of the existing research as possible so as to provide as complete a picture as possible with a view to discern as robust as possible lessons. These should also insofar as relevant be incorporated in the next audits.

Keywords: democratic audit, European Union, emergency politics, legitimacy, pandemic

1. See the research paper by Vivien Schmidt (2023) for process traces of several important decision-making processes during Covid 19.

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to discern relevant policy recommendations for improving democracy and legitimacy during emergency situations. That is in line with REGROUP's decision to use democratic auditing to make suggestions for evaluating public control of emergency responses to COVID-19. To that end two working papers have been published - by Fossum and Lord (2023) and by Schmidt (2023). The assessments in these working papers consist of four steps, where the three first were presented in Fossum and Lord (2023) and the fourth in Schmidt (2023). The first step was to clarify what is meant by 'democratic audit.' The second step was to establish how to adapt the democratic audit framework to the special conditions surrounding emergency politics, with particular emphasis on what the literature on emergency governance says on whether emergencies entail suspensions of law and democracy. The third step was to adapt this framework to the EU, and the fourth step was through a range of process tracing exercises to discern the legitimacy implications of the multilevel EU's crisis handling in the COVID-19 context. These steps combined with a survey of the research on how Europe has been dealing with the covid pandemic have led us to the policy recommendations that we present in this paper.

In the search for policy recommendations this paper expands well beyond REGROUP through having consulted a large body of research on the governing and democratic legitimacy implications of Covid-19. This consultation had two main aims. One was methodological: to ensure that our democratic audit framework was in synch with the general and specific findings in this large body of research. The more well-aligned with this broad body of research the more relevant and salient our democratic audit framework. The other was to ensure that the lessons we derive rest on a much wider body of research than was conducted under the auspices of REGROUP and its sister projects.²

The research we consulted included other relevant research projects, a long list of journals in law and political science, and assessments by public institutions. The journals were broadly speaking EU journals, in other words that the EU occupies a central place in what the journals publish.³ In addition, we searched the EP Library Catalogue. The relevant search keywords were chosen to cover the core research themes, and included: COVID-19, pandemic, syndemic, emergency, crisis in combination with one or more of the following keywords: democracy, legitimacy, govern, governance, governing, and government. Articles dealing with other crises than COVID-19 were excluded, and articles not relating to democracy and governing, for instance those with a medical focus,

2. [PanDDemiC - Pandemic data and documentation centre](#)

3. Relevant journals were: Journal of European Public Policy (JEPP), Journal of European Integration (JEI), Journal of Common Market Studies (JCMS), West European Politics, Journal of Contemporary European Studies, (JCES), Modern Law Review (MLR), European Journal of Political Research (EJPR), European Journal of Political Theory (EJPT), European Law Open, European Law Journal, Journal of Peace Research, and International Journal of Public Administration.

were excluded. Articles dealing with other areas than the EU and affiliated countries were also excluded from the search.

The paper is structured as follows. The first part sums up REGROUP's approach to the study of European democracy and legitimacy in the context of crisis with particular emphasis on the democratic audit and discerns recommendations from that. This presentation is complemented with relevant findings from other non-REGROUP sources. The second part zooms in on the pandemic and draws out relevant recommendations and lessons.

Democratic audit: Why and how

Why do we need a democratic audit in order to assess the democratic legitimacy implications of COVID-19? COVID-19 as an emergency led to suspensions of basic constitutional-democratic provisions and arrangements. How serious that was requires clarification. The democratic audit along the lines that David Beetham (2005) has prescribed is a comprehensive and sophisticated approach for assessing the general quality of a given democratic system.⁴ An important rationale for applying the democratic audit to COVID-19 is that the overall quality of democracy pre-emergency matters for the governments' handling of the pandemic (Engler et al 2021: 1077).

The two main types of measures that are considered by Engler et al. are those that restrict individual freedoms and those that lead to power concentration. The article by Engler et al. reinforces the general point that we need audits of the overall quality and robustness of democracy as part of any assessment of how well democratic and legitimate member state democracies and the EU are likely to be in their responses to pandemics.⁵ How well-established democracies have survived the pandemic, without substantial damage to their democratic institutions and policies is a question to be asked not assumed. We have identified several additional assessments that also show that the quality of democratic institutions matters to the countries' COVID-19 handling (see for instance Egger 2021; Poyet et al. 2024). Chiru (2024:408) notes that: "(t)he extant research shows that parliaments were better able to fulfil their oversight roles in states with a higher quality of democracy and where constitutional and procedural rules provided more space for parliamentary scrutiny (e.g. incongruent bicameralism)." That is why we recommend the development and adjustment of democratic audit standards for evaluating the particular problem of how well democratic standards have 'survived' the pandemic. But as we have shown elsewhere (Fossum and Lord 2023), it is necessary to adapt the democratic audit to the specific context of emergency politics. Doing that

4. See also [International IDEA Handbook on Democracy Assessment | International IDEA](#)

5. A similar argument is found in Poyet et al. 2024. The analytical framework they devise has obvious elements in common with our democratic audit framework.

should help us both to understand how different democracies react and the specific conditions and challenges they grapple with during and after the emergency.

The next step is to explain in brief what we mean by a democratic audit.

What is meant by democratic audit?

The idea of democratic auditing was developed by the political philosopher and political scientist David Beetham. In various collaborations, he sought to “develop a method and a framework which can be used by citizens of any country to audit their own democracy. The point of such an Audit is to identify the most significant strengths and weaknesses as a contribution to reforming and strengthening the democratic process” (Beetham 2005: 161). Our main interest in the audit is as a method of improving theoretical understanding of what we know and believe about democracy, as well as practical understanding of what we should do about it in a particular context such as emergency politics. Assessing democracy helps constitute democracy. Standards cannot just precede assessments; they need to be recursively defined by reflection on how standards can themselves be recast by lessons from the very practices and experiences they assess.

1. *Reasoned standards.* Beetham started by defending public control with political equality as a core definition of democracy. He then went on to identify practices and further values that ‘mediate’ the delivery of public control with political equality: participation, authorisation, representation, accountability, transparency, responsiveness and solidarity (Beetham et al 2008: 22) From there, he framed up to 90 ‘indicators’ or ‘guiding questions’ (ibid) that ask how well a political system delivers public control with political equality through their mediating values.

2. *Explicit and Accountable standards.* By making indicators fully explicit, the Audit also provides a more accountable method of assessing the democratic quality of political systems. Justifying one set of indicators rather than another, or one way rather than another of framing one particular indicator, establishes an ‘Audit trail’.

3. *Coherent standards.* As Beetham put it (2008: 25), ‘our aim is to construct the assessment framework around a coherent understanding of democracy, rather than a random set of elements put together without explanation’.

4. *Comprehensive standards.* Beetham also aimed at a ‘comprehensive and systematic assessment of a country’s political life against core principles of public control with political equality’. How to make sure that everything that is important to democracy is included in any assessment? How to identify trade-offs and predicaments? How to

distinguish problems for one standard of democracy that arise in the delivery of some other 'imperative of democracy'

5. *Ideal and attainable standards.* Democracy assessment requires standards of what is good enough and not just ideal. Any method of democracy assessment needs to be complete, coherent and diagnostic enough to identify where things are getting better or worse; and where a system is failing even to attain the attainable as defined by its own standards, its own past and comparisons it itself makes with others.

6. *Measurement?* Terms much as 'Audit' or 'Indicators' might suggest measurement. Some measures plainly can tell us some things about some elements of democracy. Voter participation, support, satisfaction, and trust in democracy are examples. It would also help to locate those aspects of democracy that often are measured within a framework - such as a Democratic Audit - for assessing how democratic is a political system over all. In some ways, it is also trivially true that everything can be measured. So, for example, even the most qualitative evaluations can be turned into numbers by asking people to give scores out of ten. Yet also obvious are limits to attempts to measure, aggregate or rank democracy. Even the design of measures involves much judgement and many normative assumptions. Still more question-begging are attempts to aggregate this or that aspect of a country's political life into a single score of how democratic it is overall. How, can different elements of democracy be aggregated into an overall score where different conceptions of democracy, and different reasons for valuing it, put different weight on those elements?

7. *Social Construction.* Rather than a measure, Democratic Auditing was conceived as a help to citizens in reflecting and deciding on their own democracies: on what they value in them; on their form; and on their strengths and weaknesses. Assessing democracy helps constitute democracy. Standards cannot just precede assessments. Rather, they need to be recursively defined.

8. *A responsibility of democracy.* But above all, democracy is a form of collective decision, shared law, and shared coercion. Democracies regulate 'aspects of lives in common' (Habermas 1996). That, arguably, entails a responsibility on democracies - based in democratic principles of self-rule and non-domination - for assessing how well collective and coercive decisions can be justified as forms of self-coercion. All the more so if any one way of doing democracy pre-empts other ways of organising democracy. That a democracy should have the means of assessing itself is a part of its obligations to its citizens, and the responsibilities of citizens to one another that follow from any use they make of procedures of public control with political equality to author laws and policies that will apply to all co-citizens.

The democratic audit improves the robustness of the knowledge-base and helps clarify what are working democracies and what are not. A pan-European democratic audit will therefore ensure a coherent knowledgebase to assess the effects of emergencies against. We need two sets of knowledge to assess the democratic and governing effects of emergencies such as COVID-19. One is a comprehensive and systematized body of knowledge; the other is knowledge of changes over time.

In line with these two knowledge needs, our **first recommendation** is that the EU organizes and conducts **regular democratic audits** at the EU-level and within all member and affiliated states, including applicant states. One issue pertains to responsibility: The audits should not be an EU-alone or sole EU responsibility but should be performed in close cooperation with the EU's member states.⁶ A second issue pertains to timing: The audits would be performed so that the results would be available before each European Parliament election. A third issue pertains to who should perform the audits: The democratic audit would be conducted by a group of researchers from each member state and the EU. This could be either a fixed set of institutions within each member state or it could rotate according to local needs. These teams should be selected among only those researchers that the research community would unreservedly accept as of high independence and integrity to prevent backsliding governments from filling up rosters with their acolytes.

The audit will consist in a) gathering and systematizing existing data from government⁷ and other relevant sources, research projects and available academic research⁸; and b) generating the requisite additional data through process-tracing important decisions/ decision making processes. There is a lot of relevant information out there, so there is no need for the democratic audit to initiate all the research that it will report on. But the audit must quality-check the information it relies on. A fourth issue pertains to who should make the assessment against different audit standards and how. David Beetham used stakeholder panels. An interesting possibility might be citizens' juries/ panels of which there is experience within REGROUP. A hybrid might also be possible with something like the process traces being used to identify problems - and, better still, predicaments - some of which are then put to citizens' panels to discuss. A hybrid solution would thus allow both for some expert assessment and some 'lay' assessment.

The democratic audit would allow for a unique systematization of the existing literature and complement that with its own in certain more specific manners, which are

6. We cannot expect all member state governments to be willing to fund such a democratic audit. It is therefore a mark of the democratic quality of a member state to what extent it is willing to support such an endeavour. Those unwilling should be shamed by the EU and its supportive governments highlighting those unwilling to contribute.

7. One important source is the European Commission's Annual Rule of Law Cycle: [Annual Rule of Law Cycle - European Commission](#)

8. An important task is to survey the field to obtain all the relevant information that is out there and assess its quality. An obvious source is V-DEM: [V-Dem](#)

suggested in the below. The ongoing nature of the audit would yield ready sources of comparison, so as to develop a much greater awareness of developmental trends over time and geographic space. This would help establish the nature and magnitude of democratic backsliding, but also at the same time provide us with a clearer sense of the status of democracy in functioning democracies. That would help to avoid ‘throwing the baby out with the bathwater’ in the sense of buying into a story of democratic demise that may be overblown or overstated. There is a strong authoritarian and populist incentive in doing precisely that. The autocratic/populist argument would be that the system is broke anyway so there is no need even to think of reforming it. A regular stream of democratic audits is the single best measure for countering such claims. The democratic audit is also an important means for countering dis- and misinformation and so-called fake news. What is also important to underline is that the democratic audit a la David Beetham provides democratic accounts and stories, which allows people to understand the reasoning behind the findings it provides. That is very different from mere fact-checking. It is difficult to counter fake news and disinformation with facts only, reasoned accounts are a far more reliable antidote.

This is our first recommendation, namely to conduct regular democratic audits at the EU-level and in affiliated countries, including applicant countries. This first recommendation is **not** explicitly tied to the crisis context. Regular audits will provide the informational infrastructure and knowledge-base that specific emergency audits will depart from.

Why do we need to adapt the democratic audit to the study of emergency governance?

Crises, and even emergencies, have become recurring features of our world of fragile, interdependent systems that displace problems with and between themselves. Resource scarcity, population growth and density, environmental degradation and so forth provide ripe sources of conflict together with a less stable multipolar world. In this context of uncertainty and instability, democracies need to define what standards and procedures should apply in an emergency. That is one important set of reasons for why we should adapt democratic audits to emergency governance.

A second set of reasons pertains to the fact that whereas crises and emergencies often lead to sidelining of constitutional democratic arrangements, there are few instances of full-scale abandonment or dismantling of democracy. This makes the adaptation of the democratic audit framework to the emergency context both relevant and feasible.

A third reason for why it is important to adapt the democratic audit framework to the context of crisis/emergency pertains to the polity and policy changes that are taken

to deal with the emergency. The system is often no longer the same after the crisis/emergency. The emergency-adapted democratic audit helps establish the nature, direction, and magnitude of change effected during and after the emergency. This is not only about policy and institutional changes aimed at countering the negative effects of the pandemic. It also includes repressive measures. The pandemic provides

an opportunity for abusive governments to engage in repressive behavior without countervailing pressure from citizens and the international community. Following this logic, we expect abusive governments to be more likely to adopt restrictive policies, adopt them earlier in the course of the pandemic, and take longer to relax restrictions. Empirically, we find that governments that have recently engaged in state violence against civilians or abused citizens' human rights were about 10% more likely to enact lockdown and curfew policies" (Barcelo et al. 2022:73). Forms of surveillance used in controlling pandemics can also double as more general forms of surveillance.

Particularly in a situation where regular audits are performed for instance on a 5-year cycle, as proposed here, it will be possible to track both the changes during the emergency and how these changes resonate with the results of the pre-crisis - normal-time - audit.

Fourth, the system of democratic audits - regular audits during fixed intervals combined with emergency-related audits - will make it possible to address the infodemic that occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic.⁹

A final reason for adapting the democratic audit to emergency politics situations is that the audit will make the political dimension of emergency politics readily apparent. That is, as Kreuder-Sonnen and White (2022: 954) underline, particularly important in the EU setting. It follows from their definition of emergency politics "*as actions breaking with established norms and rules that are rationalised as necessary responses to exceptional and urgent threats...* Applied to the EU, the concept's value lies in shifting focus from managerial competence to the political aspects of decision-making under pressure.... Such a shift is the precondition for a more critical perspective: a focus on functional imperatives tends to minimise the range of thinkable outcomes, and with it the possibility to do more than applaud success or deplore failure. Such a shift is also a cue for rethinking the empirics. What constitutes a crisis and an appropriate response depends on what powerful actors wish to preserve and consolidate in the status quo." (italics in original) (See also White 2015a,b; 2020).

9. For more information on this see Mu et al. 2023.

How to adapt the democratic audit framework to emergency governance?

As we discussed in REGROUP Research Paper No. 8 (Fossum and Lord 2023), the issue of adapting the democratic audit framework to emergency governance raises a number of questions. One is about the timing of the audit and the number of audits, with the ideal one before the emergency, one during the emergency, and one after the emergency. Our recommendation of conducting regular audits would ensure that there is always one before. With regard to the context of emergency, the issue arises as to whether the same standards should be used throughout, in other words the same as are used during normal times, or whether we should change/adapt standards to the special conditions of emergency governance. If we find the need to change/adapt standards, what kind of audit standards and criteria should we use? How much should these deviate from the criteria used during normal times? One solution is to have some fixed standards and some that vary, for example, at the national and EU levels, from one emergency to another. Is there need for theoretical and methodological innovation?

When consulting the broader international body of literature, we found that there are different theoretical positions on emergency politics and governance, which vary in terms of who should be entitled to call an emergency; who should be entitled to deal with it; and under what conditions of law and democracy the emergency should be handled. The three main positions that we identified were:

1. Emergency politics as politics without law
2. Emergency politics as constitutionally regulated and constrained
3. Emergency politics as rule of law through 'regulative assumption'

The first position is closely associated with Schmittian decisionism and was rejected by us for both normative and empirical reasons. If we look at COVID-19 there were legal and democratic constraints on powerholders during the pandemic; hence we propose to adapt standards along either lines 2 or 3.

What criteria to draw from? We have derived the following from the Council of Europe (2020a,b):

1. Rule-of-law.
2. Authorisation
3. Notification
4. Necessity

5. Proportionality
6. Time limitation
7. Non-discrimination
8. Legal certainty/clarity
9. Challenge and legal remedy
10. Non-derogable rights
11. Oversight
12. Deliberation and debate

These have been elaborated in our research paper and in the Council of Europe reports, notably (2020b), and will therefore not be outlined in any further detail here. Some of these factors are also grouped under the heading of ‘democratic compensators’ by Massart et al. 2021, which they refer to as “a diverse set of decisions and practices such as the limitation of exceptional measures in time, clauses conditioning their inclusion in ordinary law to parliamentary votes, extended delays for administrative or legal acts, and online communal councils thought of as accountability mechanisms set up to justify exceptional measures.”

What is important for our purpose is to show that there is considerable support for this approach to outline specific criteria and democratic compensators both within and without REGROUP. For instance, in REGROUP’s Policy Paper 2 by Niels Kirst entitled “Best practices and key takeaways for liberal-constitutional democracies after the COVID-19 pandemic”, Kirst provides the following recommendations that dovetail well with our analysis:

- **Maintaining Transparency and Accountability in Executive Measures:** Transparency and accountability are crucial in maintaining public trust during emergencies. Therefore, governments should provide transparent and timely information about the rationale and evidence behind emergency measures. Independent oversight bodies should monitor and report on the implementation of these measures.
- **Ensuring Proportionality in Emergency Measures via the Legislative Branch:** Emergency measures must be proportionate to the threat faced and should not unreasonably restrict fundamental rights. Thus, regular review and ongoing oversight through parliaments are essential. Therefore, governments should enact emergency legislation that includes precise, time-bound limits and requires periodic review.

- **Protecting Fundamental Rights and Freedoms via the Judicial Branch:** During emergencies, the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms must be upheld as far as possible. Therefore, any emergency measures should be designed to infringe upon fundamental rights as minimal as possible. Courts must continue operating to safeguard these rights by providing avenues for judicial review and redress.
- **Strengthening Public Health Legislation on the Member State Level:** Comprehensive and adaptable public health legislation is essential for an effective crisis response. The pandemic has shown that public health laws must be regularly updated, ensuring they can handle various scenarios and threats. Therefore, Member States should update their health legislation including lessons from the Covid-19 pandemic.
- **Enhancing Coordination on the European Level:** Effective crisis management requires coordination and cooperation between different levels of government. Thus, the EU should establish clear frameworks for intergovernmental cooperation between the Member States. This enables streamlined responses and reduces conflicts between European, national, and local authorities.
- **Promoting Collaboration on the International Level:** Pandemics are global challenges that require international cooperation and solidarity. Therefore, the EU should engage in international organisations, frameworks, and agreements to share information, resources, and best practices. Participation in global health initiatives and critical compliance with international health regulations are crucial.

In addition to these recommendations, we would add the need to focus especially on non-member states in the EU's immediate neighbourhood. Brexit has made that much more important. There are lessons to be learned about coordinating with immediate neighbours from the difference between Norway and the UK, and how they worked or in competition with the EU. In addition, EU enlargement must be included. The assessment of these countries would foster collaboration with and empowerment of local researchers working on democracy in enlarging countries. That would provide an important check on the way the EU's conditionality process is conducted, as well.

Towards a democratic audit of emergency governance in the EU

The next step is to adapt the democratic governance framework to the EU since the EU is distinctive, in several important respects. It is a distinctive polity or political system given that it is neither a state nor an international organization but encompasses elements of both in a unique mixture (Fabbrini 2015, 2019; Fossum 2020). The EU is also distinctive in the role it plays in emergency politics. The EU's role is mainly that of co-

ordination whereas the member states do the coercion (Lord et al. 2023). Kirst in one of his recommendations usefully includes the European level and underlines the need for enhancing coordination. An important question in that connection is whether the EU's role should be mainly confined to coordination or whether there should be more direct EU 'bite' through granting the EU coercive measures.

There is no doubt that the EU-level must be included in a democratic audit. The audit therefore must be multilevel. A democratic audit that includes the EU is both possible and important because the EU is committed to democratic standards by its own treaties. Further, the EU is a complex system that needs to be assessed both as a whole and in its parts to locate the source(s) of any problems. But we also need to consider it as a whole to double check that problems in the parts are not delivered elsewhere in the EU's political order. As noted, the EU has distinctive features, it is not only a distinct hybrid but also a fairly unsettled political order - crisis-driven change has long been part of its development. These reflections underline that the audit needs to include explicit attention to the **polity** or the system of governance and how that changes over time. The focus must therefore be not only on politics and power but also on the nature and evolution of the governing unit itself.

Based on these observations we conclude that the context of emergency thus requires two adaptations of the democratic audit: a) to the context of emergency politics, and b) to the distinct political-constitutional system of the EU (Fossum and Lord 2023) .

Our **second recommendation** is consistent with these two adaptations and pertains to devising a supplemental audit when a major crisis that can also be understood to inaugurate a mode of emergency politics strikes. The audit will be devised with a view to take explicitly into account the gravity of the situation and how invasive the emergency measures will be. The more the emergency leads to actions with bearings on basic constitutional-democratic principles, procedures and practices, the more care the auditors must take to ensure that the criteria are properly tailored to the specifics of the situation. The magnitude of departure from normality can be tracked since there is a system of regular audits every five years. Taken together this arrangement ensures that we will be able to establish whether there are developments in a democratically positive or negative direction before as well as after the emergency. Undertaking such audits is a resource-demanding task; hence we need to be sure that the additional emergency audit is really warranted. The auditors must determine when a crisis or emergency is grave enough to require initiating a supplemental audit. Ideally there should be a set of criteria for establishing that, if possible. The supplemental audit represents an explicit adaptation of the democratic audit to the emergency context, and the specific design of that will be tailored to the emergency.

How and what to study?

The emergency audit will be tailored to each emergency, and since each emergency is unique, there is no assurance that the methodology that is used will be the same. In the following, as a proposal we suggest that every audit should at least contain the following elements. First is a set of dimensions that the cases are assessed against. These were listed in the above and have been derived from the Council of Europe and are corroborated by additional research, including REGROUP's (see also REGROUP Policy Papers 1-3 by Cincirpini 2024, Kirst 2024 and Capati et al. 2024).

It is natural that future emergency audits take current recommendations into special consideration. Consider for instance the recommendations that Capati et al. (2024) have set forth with regard to increasing EU resilience:

- The EU should establish innovative fiscal tools to prepare for the next macro-economic crisis.
- Member states should ensure they have dedicated units to effectively mitigate the adverse effects experienced by professionals who rely on short-term contracts during crises and emergencies.
- During emergency politics, the European Council should focus on agenda-setting and remain accountable to the European Commission, Council and European Parliament throughout the lawmaking process.
- National parliaments should continue to be involved even during emergency circumstances.
- Discursive legitimization of executive action should be enhanced.
- To enhance the framework for crisis governance, management, and response, the EU should persist in adopting anticipatory governance tools and foster international cooperation in this area.
- To enhance its global influence during crisis and emergencies, the EU should develop tools and procedures to strengthen internal cohesion among member states.

We would like to amplify the point about the need for parliaments to continue to operate during the emergency. Parliaments should avail themselves of new technologies to ensure scrutiny, debate, and representation throughout the emergency.

In addition to taking properly into account established indicators and recommendations, process tracing of key decisions (more on that below) is a very useful approach for getting a clearer understanding of the governing and democratic legitimacy aspects of emergency situations.

A third and complementary approach could be to conduct a comparative study of multi-level EU legitimacy during the pandemic. The comparison is an obvious complement to the country case studies that the audit brings forth.

The fourth and final element we address is to discern the most relevant lessons from the emergency and its handling. These are when relevant incorporated into the general audit framework and/or into the design of the next round of emergency politics audits.

We have already presented the list of indicators and therefore discuss the remaining three elements here. With regard to **process tracing**, we draw on Vivien Schmidt's paper entitled "Power and Legitimacy during Emergency Politics" (REGROUP Research Paper No. 12) because she here applied the audit framework to the COVID-19 crisis by means of process tracing.

Our **third recommendation** is to conduct focused process-tracing exercises in all member states and at the EU-level in connection with an emergency. We have also proposed process-tracing during the regular audits. Such a process-tracing exercise can be conducted in lieu of a more comprehensive emergency-adapted audit or even in conjunction with it.

With regard to the third element, that of **comparative studies of EU legitimacy** we refer to the following example from REGROUP, as a possible element to include in a democratic audit. Grimm et al. in REGROUP Research Paper No. 14. entitled "Perceptions of EU and member state legitimacy in times of crisis: a citizens' perspective", address the following two questions: How do citizens perceive the legitimacy of national executives and EU institutions' actions in times of crisis and how far do legitimacy perspectives differ in ordinary times versus in times of crisis?

With regard to the fourth and final element that we mentioned above, that of **lessons**, we draw on the findings from the broader body of research on the nature and effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Our survey of the literature has discerned lessons that we have lumped under broad categories such as the nature of the emergency, effects on and lessons for structures and policies; the nature and scope for learning; and the nature and effects of crisis communication. The brief literature review we provide in the below shows that the literature already gives us some theoretical expectations that we can look out for in the process traces.

With regard to the nature of the emergency, it is important to clarify whether it is in its nature and effects symmetrical or asymmetrical. Schramm (2022) underlines that the corona pandemic emanated from outside the EU, and there is consensus in the literature that it represented a symmetrical shock. That does not mean that the effects are the same or equal; it means that the sources of differences lie in the receiving states, not in the pandemic itself. Further, the fact that the pandemic was a symmetric shock

did not mitigate the effects of the EU's distinctive multilevel configuration and how that shaped emergency politics dynamics, which were profoundly shaped by the fact that states are closely interconnected within the European context. In order to capture that Kreuder-Sonnen and White (2022) distinguish between four types of exceptionalism: supranational, multilateral, unilateral, and domestic. They note that “(d)ifferent forms of emergency politics affect different legal and political orders in the first instance. While unilateral exceptionalism strikes EU rules and norms directly, domestic exceptionalism strikes those of a given memberstate. Its initial significance may be local. But as an interdependent order, one where exceptionalism migrates easily from one setting to another, the EU as a whole tends soon to be affected. With multilateral and supranational exceptionalism especially, the legacies tend to be wide-ranging” (Kreuder-Sonnen and White 2022: 960).

The EU's distinct multilevel structural configuration does not only generate and amplify effects across governing units; there are also path dependencies at play. Cox and Kurzer (2024:610) note that “the EU response to the COVID-19 crisis follows a pattern much like its response to earlier public health threats. Though each time the EU commits to being prepared for the next cross-border threat to health, as the immediate crisis recedes, so does the momentum to build the necessary administrative capacity, leaving the EU unprepared to take a leadership role when the next public health crisis emerges.” This important observation gives rise to the important lesson that we need to be aware of the dangers of ending up like generals fighting the last war.

The constrained nature of the EU's crisis response that the authors point to may relate to the nature of the bodies that were central in the crisis handling. Schramm and Wessels (2022) underline the central role of the European Council as a driver and as a creator of links between levels.¹⁰ That leadership led to the EU creating new arrangements in need of democratic control and legitimation.¹¹ How can we square these seemingly different accounts with one highlighting path dependence and the other the development of the Next Generation EU, a new fiscal instrument? The simple answer is that both are correct because they deal with different aspects of the EU's emergency politics responses. Further, the fact of path dependence does not detract from the EU system being less fixed and more malleable than well-functioning states; hence the need for the democratic audit to take explicitly into account the EU polity as it passes through the emergency.

Some studies also focus on the scope for learning during the pandemic. Immonen et al. (2024: 1215) identify “three distinct logics - selfishness, emulation and coordination - taking shape, which together form a framework of cyclical Europeanisation. Efforts to cope with the pandemic made tensions between the Commission and its self-interested member states apparent. However, the member states were simultaneously able to

10. See also Van Middelaar's (2019) account of the centrality of the European Council.

11. For a discussion of these measures see Schramm 2022.

learn from each other and thus emulate policy practices under conditions of uncertainty. Hence, regardless of the problems incurred, the ability to revert the tensions between the different logics of action and combine them pragmatically has reinforced some sense of Europeanisation within the European polity. External shocks intensify the cycles through which Europeanisation evolves and materialises, and bring to light the EU's ability to act and react, improvise and adapt." A similar emphasis on policy learning is found in Serban (2023).

With regard to possible lessons pertaining to communication, Schnabel et al. (2024) in their article entitled "Multilevel governance and political leadership: crisis communication in Germany, Italy, and the United Kingdom during the COVID-19 pandemic" underline the need for consistency in crisis communication because that is an important part of political leadership during crises. The authors find that: "centralisation does not automatically lead to consistent crisis communication. At the same time, decentralised decision making does not necessarily undermine consistency. Overall, crisis communication tends to be more consistent when leaders coordinate crisis management."

A further consideration is to avoid what Baekkeskov et al. (2021: 1321) term 'discourse monotony'. The authors *present* "two ideal-types that discourse may tend toward. One is pluralism, which includes authoritative voices that represent viable alternative policies and credible reasons for them. The opposite is monotony, where authoritative voices offer credible reasons for one policy option only." The authors note that "skews toward discourse monotony create risks to democratic legitimacy and long-term response efficacy." The broader implication is that issue framing and discussion of alternatives matter for the legitimacy of government responses to emergency situations.

Mu et al. (2023) argue that the pandemic «led to an infodemic where an overwhelming amount of COVID-19 related content was being disseminated at high velocity through social media." This prompted the authors to make a misinformation classification dataset, which will be a useful addition to any democratic audit.

Our **fourth recommendation** is to collect and systematize lessons and best practices as part of conducting the emergency audit. The lessons should be incorporated in the new audit. In that sense auditing serves as a constant learning process. Insofar as we find competing accounts of events or developments, we need to work out which accounts are most relevant and credible. Doing that also improves the quality of the auditing process.

To sum up we present the following four sets of policy recommendations:

1. Conduct regular democratic audits in the multilevel EU and affiliated and applicant states on a five-year rotating basis
2. Adapt the audit to emergency circumstances when necessary

3. Undertake process-tracing of key decisions during (and after) an emergency
4. Derive lessons from the emergency and incorporate those in the regular and emergency audit as relevant

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to discern relevant policy recommendations for improving democracy and legitimacy during emergency situations. That is in line with REGROUP's decision to use democratic auditing to make suggestions for evaluating public control of emergency responses to COVID-19. To that end two working papers have been published - by Fossum and Lord (2023) and by Schmidt (2023). The assessments in these working papers consisted of four steps, where the three first were presented in Fossum and Lord (2023) and the fourth in Schmidt (2023). The first step was to clarify what is meant by 'democratic audit.' The second step was to establish how to adapt the democratic audit framework to the special conditions surrounding emergency politics, with particular emphasis on what the literature on emergency governance says on whether emergencies entail suspensions of law and democracy. The third step was to adapt this framework to the EU, and the fourth step was through a range of process tracing exercises to discern the legitimacy implications of the multilevel EU's crisis handling in the COVID-19 context. These steps combined with a survey of the research on how Europe has been dealing with the covid pandemic have led us to the policy recommendations that we present in this paper.

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